
Hermeneutic Approaches in the Development of Mother Tongue Education: Theory and Practice

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Abstract: To be able to use the scientific and theoretical foundations of mother tongue education, the most convenient and modern methods of teaching at different stages of education, to teach the methodology of teaching the uzbek language based on the professional requirements for future teachers of the uzbek language. It consists of teaching effective methods, forms and methods of teaching the content of the language at the level of modern requirements, highlighting the pedagogical and methodological possibilities of their implementation. The methods and methods of teaching the uzbek language to students, their theoretical foundations, the hermeneutic approach, the role of the uzbek language in the educational content, the set of BKM's given to students at each level of the uzbek language, theoretical knowledge of the theoretical foundations of innovative pedagogical and methodological activities to work on the tasks, to achieve full mastery of the practice of the uzbek language educational content methodology with the students. The hermeneutic teaching on the development of a scientific worldview in the uzbek language education is reflected in the article.

Key words: Language, thinking, coherence, word, tool, product, material entity, learning process, uzbek language unit, discourse, student, hermeneutic teaching, acquisition, language as a social phenomenon, quality, introduction, important importance, uzbek language educational content, scientific outlook, clear understanding, help.

The "Action Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017–2021" highlights the priority of improving the education system and expanding access to quality educational services. Within this framework, independent learning assignments hold a central position in the modular-credit education system. In Uzbekistan, the subject Methodology of Teaching the Native Language for future native language teachers is studied through a credit-based education system. Learning materials for this subject are designed for independent study, and practical tasks are carried out individually by students. This approach equips future native language teachers with the ability to apply the scientific and methodological foundations of native language education and employ the most effective and modern teaching methods at various educational stages.

Significant attention is being paid to the introduction of the modular-credit system for prospective native language teachers, with the aim of fostering students' independent study skills. This effort is aligned with building the foundation for a New Renaissance by creating the pedagogical and methodological conditions necessary for their development. The methodology incorporates a competency-based approach, emphasizing the development of linguistic competencies during classroom activities to enhance students' communicative skills.

The subject Methodology of Teaching the Native Language is grounded in a methodological competency-based approach. It aims to develop linguistic competencies in ways that contribute to improving students' communicative skills. Clear skill requirements—such as listening comprehension, speaking, reading, and writing—highlight the need to further expand the

methodological opportunities for teaching these skills effectively. This necessitates the development of a didactic system and a technological model to enhance methodological competence, along with refining the pedagogical and didactic conditions for its practical implementation.

The article is informed by key directives such as the Presidential Decree No. PF-4947 (February 7, 2017) on the "Action Strategy for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan," Decree No. PF-5313 (January 25, 2018) on "Measures to Radically Improve the System of General Secondary, Specialized Secondary, and Vocational Education," and Decree No. PF-5850 (October 22, 2019) on "Measures to Radically Increase the Prestige and Role of the Uzbek Language as a State Language." Additionally, it considers the "Concept for the Development of the Public Education System in Uzbekistan Until 2030" (Decree No. PF-5712, April 29, 2019) and the Presidential Resolution No. RQ-4623 (February 27, 2020) on "Measures for the Further Development of Pedagogical Education." The article also reflects on subsequent directives, such as the January 28, 2022, Decree No. PF-60 on the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026" and other regulatory documents. This study aims to contribute, to some extent, to fulfilling the objectives outlined in these legal and normative documents concerning the development of the native language and the enhancement of language policy.

The content of native language education is aligned with the tasks set by the state for methodologists at this stage of societal development. These tasks are multifaceted and aim to enhance students' intellectual development while fostering ideological-political, moral, aesthetic, and labor education. As a result of learning the content of native language education, students develop skills to express their thoughts grammatically correctly, stylistically clearly, meaningfully, with proper intonation, and to write accurately according to spelling norms. This goal reflects the unique nature of the native language as a subject and is implemented in conjunction with methodological objectives aimed at developing the student as an individual.

The knowledge conveyed in the content of native language education encompasses various aspects of the language. These include:

Phonetics and Graphics: Understanding the sound structure of the language and methods of representing sounds in written form.

Grammar (Morphology and Syntax): Knowledge about word inflection and the connection between words in sentences.

Word Formation: The morphological composition of words and methods of word formation.

Lexicology: The lexical-semantic grouping of words.

Orthography and Punctuation: Principles of correct spelling and the usage of punctuation marks.

This knowledge manifests first in the understanding of grammatical, phonetic, and word formation concepts, and second in mastering graphic, orthographic, and punctuation rules. Additionally, the content integrates phonetic, graphic, morphological, syntactic, and other language skills.

The process of learning the language also involves developing interdisciplinary skills common to other subjects. In pedagogy, such interdisciplinary skills include analysis, synthesis, abstraction (mentally conceptualizing linguistic phenomena), generalization, classification, and comparison. Developing these skills in students based on hermeneutic teaching methods is effective. This approach stimulates their learning activity and creates opportunities for successfully mastering knowledge

In the content of native language education, specialized skills are developed alongside interdisciplinary skills without separating them, ensuring their integrated growth within the educational process. Knowledge based on hermeneutic principles, which contributes to the development of specialized skills, is documented in curricula, syllabi, and state educational

standards. For first- and second-year students, the selected knowledge serves as a foundation for developing graphical and orthographic competencies, ensuring conscious mastery of the subject.

In phonetics and graphics, students acquire knowledge that helps them understand the sound composition of words, the specific features of vowels and consonants, and the significance of sounds in distinguishing meanings. This knowledge, grounded in hermeneutic principles, also enables students to consciously identify the relationship between the sound and graphic forms of words, enhancing their ability to write words correctly. Similarly, in morphology, the chosen knowledge has practical significance, ensuring conscious understanding and correct usage of words. From the first year, students systematically study parts of speech (nouns, adjectives, numerals, pronouns, verbs) at various levels.

In syntax, the curriculum includes knowledge about sentences as units of speech, the connection between words in sentences, and primary and secondary sentence components. Regarding word structure, students are provided with sufficient knowledge to understand the key characteristics of morphemes, their significance, and their mutual influence within words, facilitating correct spelling practices. Although the “Lexicon” section is not presented separately in the curriculum, students gain information about the lexical-semantic groups of words (synonyms, antonyms) and their meanings during the study of parts of speech and word structure.

The roots of hermeneutics trace back to ancient Western and Eastern cultures. However, as an independent field, it emerged in the 19th century, associated with the work of German philosophers Friedrich Schleiermacher and Wilhelm Dilthey. Subsequent developments were shaped by scholars like Martin Heidegger, Hans-Georg Gadamer, Paul Ricoeur, and Mikhail Bakhtin. At the heart of hermeneutics lies the issue of understanding. Friedrich Schleiermacher described hermeneutics as the “art of understanding written texts,” emphasizing that any written text has a dual nature: on the one hand, it is part of a linguistic system; on the other, it represents the creative output of an individual. Therefore, hermeneutics addresses two interconnected tasks: first, examining linguistic expressions within the text as components of a language system (“grammatical interpretation”), and second, understanding the unique individual behind the text (“psychological interpretation”).

Wilhelm Dilthey, in his *philosophy of life*, regarded hermeneutics not merely as a branch of epistemology but as the foundation of the humanities (or “sciences of the mind”). He argued that understanding is the sole means of adequately expressing the entirety of life, demonstrating that life can only be comprehended through understanding. As noted by M.E. Akhmedova, any creative output of an individual represents an objectification of life; a person understands in another what they can comprehend within themselves. Thus, life becomes shaped by the concepts of the one perceiving and understanding it.

Hans-Georg Gadamer's transition to philosophy is closely associated with Martin Heidegger, who viewed “understanding” not as knowledge but as a mode of existence. In the context of literary studies, traditional hermeneutics—the theory of interpreting (“understanding”) texts—is more relevant than philosophical hermeneutics. A person's relationship with existence, their understanding of it, and their unique circumstances, such as the environment in which they live and work, determine how a text should be interpreted in higher education. This means each individual must interpret and understand a text in their own way.

Efforts to enhance the quality of education in Uzbekistan are focusing on improving the methodological and instructional support to ensure students achieve the required proficiency in their native language. Educational initiatives are being implemented to strengthen the practical aspects of Uzbek language instruction. This aligns with the directive to “radically improve the quality of teaching the Uzbek language and literature at all levels of the education system and to train highly qualified specialists in this field” [1:127]. Achieving this objective requires prioritizing the interpretation, analysis, and explanation of texts, highlighting the importance of

hermeneutics. Consequently, the study of hermeneutics has gained significant traction among Uzbek scholars.

Prominent Uzbek literary scholars such as Bahodir Karim [8:7], I. Rahimov, A. O‘tamurodov [9:146], N. Shermuhamedova [10:237], and Q. Nazarov [12:189] have explored specific aspects of hermeneutic theory. Bahodir Karim, as a literary critic, views hermeneutics primarily as a tool for studying literary works [8:9]. He also discusses the "Eastern Hermeneutic Tradition," emphasizing that it did not follow the same developmental trajectory as Western hermeneutics. However, he notes that what is referred to as "Eastern Hermeneutics," particularly the interpretation of the meanings of the Qur'an (tafsir), does not fully correspond to the philosophical hermeneutics under discussion. This is because tafsir (Qur'anic exegesis) and philosophical hermeneutics differ significantly.

N. Shermuhamedova analyzes the hermeneutic foundations of understanding and explanation from a philosophical-methodological perspective, underscoring the crucial role of understanding in grasping the meaning of a given phenomenon [11:205]. Furthermore, scholars such as M. Abdullayeva, Sh. Jabborov, G. Navro‘zova, and G. Yunusova have also contributed to discussions on the significance and historical roots of hermeneutics in scientific inquiry through their research and articles [13:27-29]. In Uzbek linguistics, the foundational ideas regarding text and text theory were first introduced by academician G‘. Abdurahmonov. Later, scholars such as A. G‘ulomov and M. Asqarova, in their textbook *Modern Uzbek Literary Language*, recognized the text as a linguistic unit. Subsequent researchers, including I. Rasulov, M. To‘qsonov, and M. Mukarramov, conducted studies on various aspects of texts.

G.N. Navruzova and G.S. Yunusova emphasized the importance of studying the social function of the native language in higher education, which holds significant methodological value. They categorized the functions of language into the following groups:

1. **Communicative function**
2. **Social function**
3. **Expressive function**
4. **Aesthetic function**
5. **Gnoseological function**

However, according to Navruzova and Yunusova's own classification, six functions of language are identified:

1. **Emotive function:** Focused on the sender and conveying emotions.
2. **Cognitive function:** Directed at the recipient to evoke a specific response or understanding.
3. **Poetic function:** Concerned with the form of information.
4. **Metalinguistic function:** Pertaining to the language system itself.
5. **Phatic function:** Maintaining and facilitating communication.
6. **Referential function:** Focused on describing reality.

Among the notable research from the early 20th century to the present, Sh.Sh. Yuldasheva's work *Scientific and Methodological Foundations for Developing Students' Speech Skills in State Language Education* [14:80–82], and studies by M.E. Akhmedova and G.K. Rasulova, such as their research on enriching students' vocabulary in native language education [2:18], have significantly contributed to the field. These studies focus on developing students' Uzbek language proficiency.

In the hermeneutic study of texts, it is critical to examine all aspects of the native language curriculum in an interconnected manner. At each stage of learning, the methodological development of knowledge about phonetics, lexicon, grammar, and word formation is of

paramount importance. This integrative approach ensures that students’ understanding of text is both comprehensive and methodologically grounded.

Table 1. “Model for Enhancing Hermeneutic Competencies in Mother Tongue Education”

In the system of teaching the native language, understanding the art of knowing, comprehending, reading, and writing through texts is primarily implemented based on critical thinking. Critical thinking is the process of analyzing phenomena and events by drawing rational conclusions, providing substantiated evaluations and interpretations, and applying the results to situations and problems. Generally, critical thinking is regarded as a higher level of reasoning compared to pre-critical thinking. Hermeneutics, on the other hand, is the art of understanding and interpretation. It is an art that reflects how a person lives, their ideals, and worldview. Each individual lives, thinks, and understands existence in their own way based on their comprehension. Applying the principles of multidimensionality proves to be effective in this context.

1. Developing the Content of Native Language Education focuses on enriching vocabulary and forming grammatical knowledge. **2. Developing Logical Thinking** Engages with problem-solving situations involving numbers and logical games. **3. Developing Visual-Spatial Intelligence** Involves projects and visual presentations. **4. Developing Musical Intelligence** includes rhythmic movements and musical texts. **5. Developing Kinesthetic Intelligence** incorporates quick question-and-answer sessions and pantomime activities. **6. Developing Social Intelligence** emphasizes group games, project creation, and dialog-based teaching. **7. Developing Intrinsic Intelligence** focuses on personal impressions, poetry, storytelling, and essay writing.

Logical thinking and the hermeneutic approach enable individuals to perform operations such as making logical conclusions and processing information. The hermeneutic perspective is so widely spread that it inevitably encompasses the experience of beauty in nature and art.

Three aspects of human development:

- **Language:** A key form of human cognitive activity.
- **Consciousness:** Inextricably linked to language, it is not only the medium of labor but also a universal means of human interaction and communication.
- **Labor:** Develops and enriches language.

A literary text represents a unique way for a person to know and perceive existence. All information received from the external world evolves based on the worldview of the creator. The hermeneutic approach to logical thinking includes "the obligation to use reason in shaping our beliefs." Accordingly, the goal of modern teaching is to teach understanding.

In the process of speech, focus is placed on the graphic encoding of sound symbols. Understanding a text requires correct expression in speech and emphasizes communicative and creative abilities.

Understanding the semantics of socio-cultural gaps and reflections by uncovering and addressing them in speech. Expressing ideas through speech requires the representation of thought using sound codes, ensuring compliance with the norms of literary language.

Students are required to strictly adhere to two standards—intonation and grammatical rules—to properly comprehend the text. The use of socio-cultural elements in various forms of speech activity is also emphasized.

The hermeneutic approach fosters the development of skills to understand the socio-cultural semantic roles in specific texts. It enables the analytical process of reflection and addresses challenges through a competency-based approach to the lexical and semantic aspects of texts, thereby enhancing cognitive awareness of the world. Grammatical norms are directly related to the correct use of subjects, predicates, and case suffixes. Adhering to these two rules forms the foundation of speech culture and text comprehension.

Students' ability to approach native language education as an interconnected and holistic phenomenon requires the hermeneutic method. T.T. Koziyeyeva highlights that a hermeneutic approach to studying native language content enhances students' speech development and their listening and comprehension skills. Utilizing hermeneutic techniques fosters better understanding and problem-solving in the teaching process [16:39-45].

Core structure of the "Grammar, Orthography, and Speech Development" section. Each group covers the following parts:

1. **Sounds and Letters**
2. **Words**
3. **Sentences**
4. **Coherent Speech**

The main topics are studied progressively across all four levels, ensuring grammatical understanding is built incrementally. Leading topics are selected for each grade, which align with the principle of step-by-step consistency. Implementing such requirements for native language teachers necessitates clearly defining teaching content and adopting innovative teaching approaches.

As stated in the state educational standards, every stage of native language education—such as in Karakalpak language instruction—must meet pedagogical, methodological, and didactic requirements. These requirements ensure complete harmony, balance, and alignment within philological education. In this regard, modernizing the structure and content of philological education is essential. Utilizing modern pedagogical technologies enhances the development of native language instruction. The methodological, didactic, and pedagogical requirements set for the 1st to 4th stages of language education focus on:

1. Expanding students' cognitive skills.
2. Encouraging independent thinking.
3. Improving the ability to understand others' viewpoints.
4. Developing the ability to express thoughts orally and in writing.
5. Facilitating confident communication skills for interaction in society.

Skills for written expression. Students are expected to acquire the following skills:

- **Logical Coherence:** Ensuring that ideas are presented logically.
- **Relevance and Completeness:** Aligning the description with the topic and presenting it thoroughly.
- **Use of Expressive Means:** Employing the stylistic tools of the native language effectively.
- **Orthographic Literacy:** Demonstrating proficiency in spelling and grammar rules.

In conclusion, it must be emphasized that developing the content of native language education plays a crucial role in achieving these objectives. Methodically accomplishing these tasks largely depends on accurately defining the content of native language education. Only when the content is defined precisely and scientifically, fulfilling the methodological, didactic, and pedagogical requirements can be fully achieved. It is well-known that the native language education content specified in the State Educational Standards (DTS) is reflected in the curriculum and textbooks through clearly defined topics and language materials. These elements must complement one another, functioning as interdependent components.

In summary, the development of native language education content has been continuously refined based on many years of observation, research, and analysis conducted by methodological scholars. Special attention has been given to the practical significance of native language teaching, ensuring that it remains a vital area of focus.

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